

Physicochemical Properties of Silver Tungstate

P. K. SINHAMAHAPATRA* and P. K. BHATTACHARYA**

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005, (India)

Manuscript received 24 April 1978, revised 24 October 1978, accepted 12 March 1979

The method of preparation of silver tungstates have been described and the results of Differential Thermal Analysis, Thermogravimetric, Infra-red, X-ray diffraction and magnetic susceptibility measurement studies of silver tungstates and the thermal decomposition products have been reported.

SILVER tungstates are reported to be fairly active for removal of thiophene from benzene¹ and for other catalytic reactions². Not enough literature is available on the systematic physicochemical properties of these systems. In an attempt to study the reduction characteristics, Rabes et al³ identified Ag and AgWO₃ at 580°. The method of preparation has already been described by Huttig et al⁴. The pH dependence on the preparation of the tungstate has been observed by a few workers^{5,6}. Klikorka et al⁷ noticed that silver tungstate (Ag₂WO₄) had an exponential temperature dependence of conductivity typical of semi-conductors. In the present note, the results on the method of preparation, differential thermal analysis (DTA), thermogravimetry (TG), Infra-red (IR), X-ray diffraction (XRD) and magnetic susceptibility of fresh silver tungstate and its various thermal transition products have been reported.

Experimental

All the reagents employed during the investigation were of AnalaR grade.

Preparation :

100 ml of sodium tungstate dihydrate solution saturated at room temperature (6.6 g/100 ml. water) were added slowly (5 ml at a time) to a solution of silver nitrate (6.8. g/200 ml water) followed by digestion for 30 min at two different pH 7.0, 8.0-10.0 of the final mixture at 50°-60°. The substance was allowed to settle, filtered, washed repeatedly with hot water until free from adsorbed soluble impurities, then dried in an air-oven at 110°.

Chemical Analysis :

Ag⁺ in solution was analysed as AgCl by precipitation with HCl (2N) and calcination at 100°. W⁺⁶ in solution was analysed as WO₃ by precipitation with HCl and HNO₃ (50 : 50) in presence of

quinine and calcination at 700°-800°. The presence of water was tested by estimation of hydrogen using Coleman Carbon-Hydrogen Analyser. The tungstate was subjected to the usual test with Zinc-Uranil acetate for detection of sodium ions.

Procedure :

DTA of this tungstate was carried out using a manually operated DTA apparatus, as reported by Bhattacharyya et al^{8,9}. TG of this system was carried out using a Stanton Mass Flow Thermobalance with programmed heating rate 6.5°/min in an air atmosphere. IR absorption spectra of silver tungstate pretreated at temperatures 110°, 220°, 570° and 630° (for 2 hr in each case) were taken using a Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer (Model No. 257) in nujol medium. The IR spectrum was scanned in the region 4000-625 cm⁻¹. XRD patterns of the above mentioned samples were obtained using General Electric Diffractometer with nickel filtered CuK_α radiation. Magnetic susceptibilities of the same samples were measured using a Farady magnetic balance system at 24° using Hg [Co(NCS)₄] as calibrant.

Results and Discussion

The chemical composition of this tungstate is established as Ag₂WO₄ in both the pH regions (Ag-46.52%, W-39.69%, H₂O-nii).

The results of thermal analysis of this compound are shown in Fig. 1. The DTA curve shows a very weak exothermic peak at 160° followed by an exothermic base-line drift within the temperature range 220°-560° and a sharp endothermic change at 620°. The TG curve records a total weight-loss amounting to 0.6% within 240°-360° before and after of which the weight-loss is almost nil.

The results of IR studies of silver tungstate heated at different transition temperatures are shown

* Present Address : Steel Authority of India Ltd, Rourkela Steel Plant, Research and Control Laboratory, Rourkela-769 011, Orissa (India). (To whom correspondence should be addressed).

** Present Address : Research and Control Laboratory, Tata Iron & Steel Company (TISCO), P. O. Burma Mines, Jamshedpur-7, Bihar (India).

Fig. 1. DTA and TG of Silver Tungstate

IR spectrum as observed in the just preceding case revealing the endothermic change at 620° to be due to melting.

The results of X-ray analysis of silver tungstate heated at different transition temperatures are shown in Table 1. The tungstate samples heated at 110° and 220° exhibit the same diffraction patterns with a number of lines of different intensities with relevance at $d=2.82 \text{ \AA}$ and 2.52 \AA . The crystal structure appears to be almost ordered at this stage. The weak exothermic change at 160° does not cause any change in the structure of the tungstate. But the 570° and 630° preheated samples display a well defined XRD patterns indicating that structure of the compound is completely ordered at this stage and that the flat exothermic change within 220°-570° is probably due to slow crystallisation and the last endothermic peak at 620° may be due to melting. No trace of decomposition products of silver tungstate could be detected by X-ray analysis at any stages of thermal treatment.

Magnetic susceptibility measurements of different tungstate samples reveal that this tungstate is diamagnetic up to melting.

Fig. 2. Infrared Spectra of Silver Tungstate

in Fig. 2. The fresh sample (without pretreatment) and that heated at 220° show in their IR spectra two significant bands at 860, and 790 cm^{-1} which are indicative of W-O stretching vibration. At 570°, however, three bands appear at 865, 800 and 745 cm^{-1} . The 790 cm^{-1} band splits into two bands, 800 and 745 cm^{-1} at this stage indicating that the 790 cm^{-1} band may be partly due to strongly adsorbed water, which at higher temperature get expelled from lattice of the compound. The 630° preheated sample exhibits almost similar

Summing up all the data, the thermal changes in silver tungstate can be expressed as follows :

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF X-RAY ANALYSIS OF SILVER TUNGSTATE HEATED AT DIFFERENT TRANSITION TEMPERATURES

Samples heated at 110° and 220°						Samples heated at 570°C					
dA°	I/I ₁	dA°	I/I ₁	dA°	I/I ₁	dA°	I/I ₁	dA°	I/I ₁	dA°	I/I ₁
8.1	vvw	2.9	vvw	1.68	w(Br)	8.1	w	2.42	vvw	1.61	wm
6.2	vw	2.82	s	1.65	vw	6.0	vvw	2.40	vvw	1.59	ms
5.6	vw	2.7	vw	1.58	vvw(Br)	5.3	m	2.35	vw	1.55	vw
5.3	w	2.62	w	1.53	vvw	4.8	vvw	2.30	vvw	1.49	vvw
3.7	vvw	2.52	ms	1.50	vvw	4.0	vw	2.25	vvw	1.47	w
3.42	vvw	2.45	vvw	1.49	vvw	3.75	vvw	2.15	vvw	1.41	wm
3.31	mw	2.16	vvw	1.41	vvw	3.48	vvw	2.08	vvw(Br)	1.37	vvw
3.08	wm	2.08	vw(Br)	1.285	vvw	3.18	vvw	2.0	ms	1.36	vvw
3.05	w	1.995	m	1.26	vvw(Br)	3.08	vw	1.95	w(Br)	1.29	wm
3.0	w	1.825	vvw	1.20	vvw	2.95	ms	1.92	vvw	1.265	m
2.95	w	1.78	vvw	1.14	vw(Br)	2.82	s	1.82	vvw	1.185	vvw
		1.72	w			2.72	ms	1.74	vvw	1.13	vvw
						2.62	vvw	1.678	m	1.10	vvw
						2.60	vvw	1.65	wm		
								1.64	vvw		

dA°=Interplanar spacing in Angstrom unit, I/I₁=Visually estimated intensities,
 s=strong, ms=medium strong, m=medium, mw=medium weak, wm weak medium, w=weak, vw=very weak,
 vvw=very very weak, Br=Broad.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Professor S. K. Bhattacharyya for his keen interest in this work and Physical Research Wing and Catalyst Section, P & D Division, F.C.I., Sindri for TG analysis. Technical help of Analytical Physics Section, Indian Institute of Petroleum, Dehra Dun for XRD studies is also acknowledged.

References

1. A. B. STILES, US PATENT, 1952, 2, 620, 363.
2. I. A. FAVORSKOYA, *Ser. Fiz. i Khim.*, 1965, 1, 137.
3. I. RABES and R. SCHENCK, *Z. Inorg. Chem.*, 1949, 259, 201.
4. G. F. HUTTIG, *Plause Ber. Pulvert.*, 1953, 1, 82.
5. D. H. BRADHURST, B. A. W. COLLIER and J. F. DUNCAN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1957, 4, 379.
6. M. C. MEHRA and K. KANT, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1963, 25, 896.
7. J. KLIKORKA, A. ČELIKOVSKY and J. HORÁK, *J. Collec. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1960, 25, 587.
8. S. K. BHATTACHARYYA and V. S. RAMACHANDRAN, *Bull. Nat. Inst. Sci.*, India, 1959, 12, 23.
9. P. K. SINHAMAHAPATRA and S. K. BHATTACHARYYA, *J. Thermal Anal.*, 1975, 8, 45.